

BIOTINE (VITAMIN B7) USE IN THE RHEUMATIC DISEASES TREATMENT: A REVIEW

Jozelio Freire de Carvalho^{a,*}

^aUniversidade Federal da Bahia, Salvador, Bahia, Brasil

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Biotine (vitamin B7) is a vitamin from the B complex, and its deficiency may be related to diabetes mellitus, alopecia, dermatitis, and immunological and neurological abnormalities. A 1mg/day dose may treat all symptoms [1]. In systemic lupus erythematosus, a recent study has shown that 78 of 130 females with this disease present biotinic deficiency [3]. In this regard, we thought it is logical to search articles on biotinic supplementation in rheumatic diseases. Following PRISMA guidelines [2], an extensive literature search in PubMed, Scielo, and LILACS was performed without any language restriction from 1965 to June 2024. We excluded review articles and in vivo and in vitro studies. Unfortunately, no article was retrieved for this review after an extensive literature search in the databases. In conclusion, no study on biotinic (vitamin B7) supplementation in patients with rheumatic diseases is available in the medical literature.

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*Corresponding author

Email address: jotafc@gmail.com (Jozelio Freire de Carvalho)